

Influence of the Hydrolysis of Gelatine on Gold Numbers and Peptisation of other Substances.

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The impurities generally found in commercial gelatine fall under two heads, ionogenic matter and non-ionogenic matter, the latter mostly produced by the partial decomposition of the gelatine. The ionogenic matter generally present are the calcium salts of phosphoric acids, the non-ionogenic matter being mostly gelatoses, intermediate hydrolysis products of gelatine. The presence of these impurities changes the properties of gelatine in a remarkable way. It was shown by Liesegang (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 88, 1) that gelatine free from these impurities is incapable of producing Liesegang structures, a certain amount of gelatose and acid being necessary. It has been found that although a small amount of gelatose can render gelatine capable of producing banded structures, the addition of acids alone cannot produce that effect. In view of the above it seemed desirable to investigate the influence of the impurities generally found in gelatine on the peptising properties of gelatine.

The gelatine was purified by washing till the ash content was below 0.1 per cent. This purified gelatine can be kept for days without developing any signs of decay. It is nevertheless undergoing a decomposition which changes its p_H value in a marked way. Hence in the following experiments immediately before use the

gelatine was washed twice with distilled water, the water being in contact with the gelatine each time for about half an hour.

To find the strength of the gelatine solutions used in these experiments, a measured volume was evaporated to dryness in an air chamber maintained at a temperature of 90-100°. Dry gelatine cannot be weighed in the ordinary way as it takes up moisture too quickly. A tube with a bulb blown at one end with a side tube furnished with a tap was used. The bulb was blown fairly thick so as to be strong enough to be able to stand the pull of the drying gelatine. After the gelatine solution had dried the tube was closed while hot and allowed to cool down to the temperature of the room. Dry air was then allowed to leak in with the help of the tap. Even small quantities of gelatine could be weighed quite consistently by this method.

A solution of colloidal gold was prepared by Zsigmondy's method, and the gold numbers of commercial and purified gelatine were determined. In every case in these experiments the final solution was prepared by diluting in the same way. In a preliminary experiment the gold numbers of purified and commercial gelatine were as follows :—

	1st set.	2nd set.
Pure gelatine	0·014	0·016
Commercial gelatine	0·022	0·028

The values for the commercial gelatine showed great fluctuation and were much higher than the values for the corresponding purified gelatine. As the commercial gelatine contained the various ionogenic impurities as well as the degradation products of gelatine no information can be obtained from the foregoing results. Hence it was decided to change the factors one at a time.

A freshly prepared sample of gelatine was taken and a solution prepared. The solution was estimated, the necessary dilution made, and the gold number determined. To determine the gold number 10 c.c. of the gold sol were thoroughly mixed with the added amount of gelatine and kept aside for about 15 minutes before the addition of the 1 c.c. of the 10 per cent. sodium chloride. The values of the gold number have all been expressed in terms of anhydrous gelatine. A portion of the same gelatine was kept apart moist for about two nights so as to undergo partial hydrolytic and other decompositions. The gold numbers of this gelatine were then determined and the following values obtained :—

Freshly purified gelatine.

Vol. gelatine added. (0·00125 %)	Colour.	Gold number.
1·0 c.c.	Blue.	
1·2 c.c.	Purple.	
1·3 c.c.	Purplish red.	0·016.
1·4 c.c.	Red.	

Same gelatine kept moist for two days.

Vol. gelatine added. (0·00125 %)	Colour.	Gold number.
0·6 c.c.	Blue	
0·7 c.c.	Bluish purple.	
0·8 c.c.	Purple.	0·01.
1·0 c.c.	No change.	

There is thus a marked difference in the values of the gold numbers which clearly shows that gelatine when

left moist for some time undergoes a change which renders it a better peptising agent.

To investigate the above point further the influence of the decomposition of gelatine brought about by free boiling of a solution of gelatine on gold numbers was investigated. A one per cent. solution of commercial gelatine was taken and boiled freely in a silica vessel, care being taken to prevent the gelatine drying on the walls of the vessel. At the end of every two hours the solution was cooled to the temperature of the room and the volume of the liquid brought back to its original value. A solution was prepared by diluting the calculated volume and the gold number determined. The results are given in the following table :—

	Time (hours).	Gold numbers.
1.	0	0·020
2.	2	0·020
3.	4	0·018
4.	6	0·014
5.	8	0·012
6.	10	0·010
7.	12	0·012
8.	14	0·018
9.	18	0·026
10.	20	0·034

From the above we see that when gelatine is freely boiled we get in the beginning an increase in the peptising properties of gelatine which, however, after a time, begins to fall and attains a value much below the initial value.

When gelatine is freely boiled it undergoes a change. A part of it is hydrolysed producing gelatoses and other intermediate hydrolytic products of gelatine. Evidently the presence of these earlier hydrolytic products of gelatine increases its peptising value as is clearly seen from the marked fall in gold numbers. On further boiling more and more of the final products of hydrolysis of gelatine are produced at the expense of the original gelatine and hence there is a rise in gold numbers.

Another possible influence of boiling is the change in size of the particles of gelatine. In the beginning boiling disintegrates any gel aggregation that might have been formed thus producing gelatine solutions containing particles of a uniform and probably smaller size. As however the above gelatine solutions were prepared in identical conditions this influence, if any, will be very small.

The question of the size of gelatine particles on its peptising properties has been thoroughly investigated by Menz (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 66, 129). He found that the gold number decreases remarkably as the original gelatine solution from which the final dilute solution is prepared gets more and more dilute. The change is due to the presence at the lower dilutions of a larger number of finer particles which are more efficient than larger particles in peptising gold sols. Menz's dilute solutions were all prepared at the room temperature. In the following experiments in order to investigate the influence of temperature on the size of the particles all the dilute solutions have been prepared at 70°.

One gram of gelatine was allowed to swell in contact with water for several hours. It was then warmed up to 70° and the volume made up very nearly up to 100 c.c. at 70°. The solution was then cooled to the room temperature and the volume accurately made up. The

same procedure was adopted to get further dilutions, the final solution being 0·001 per cent. solution. The results obtained are given in the following table :—

Original gelatine solution.	Vol. gelatine added.	Colour.	Vol. gelatine added.	Colour.
1 per cent.	1·2 c.c.	Purple	1·0 c.c.	Purple (bluish)
0·5 „	1·2 c.c.	Purplish red	1·0 c.c.	Purple (bluish)
0·1 „	1·2 c.c.	Red purplish	1·0 c.c.	Purple
0·01 „	1·2 c.c.	Red	1·0 c.c.	Purple
0·001 „	1·2 c.c.	No change.	1·0 c.c.	Purple

So far as it could be distinguished by observing the colour changes practically no decrease in the gold number with the dilution of the original gelatine solutions was observed when the dilution was done at 70°. From the above it seems reasonable to deduce that up to a concentration of 1 per cent. the particles in a gelatine solution are practically of the same size at a temperature considerably above the gelation temperature of gelatine.

Elliott and Sheppard (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 699) have, however, obtained remarkable differences in gold numbers even when the dilution was done at a temperature of 50°, which is not borne out by the above experiments. It is well known that a one per cent. gelatine solution when kept at room temperature for several hours will set into a gel. When this is shaken up with water the gel is torn into smaller fragments. If shaken for a sufficiently long time a solution is obtained which contains particles of all different sizes from about molecular dimensions to the size of about 9 μ . Menz showed by ultramicroscopic examinations that such a solution contained particles of the size 2—9 μ . The presence of coarser particles can easily be seen from the

fact that even after two hours of vigorous shaking the resulting solution contained particles big enough to be separated by an ordinary filter paper. These particles which are stopped by the filter paper may very appropriately be looked upon as fragments of the original gel which have not gone into solution. This is tantamount to saying that the final gelatine solution is actually weaker than what it is supposed to be. Consequently a higher gold number will be expected irrespective of the influence of the size of gelatine particles on its peptising properties. This should be taken into consideration when drawing any conclusions from the rise in gold numbers as obtained by Menz and repeated by others. On the other hand when the gel is warmed to a temperature of 70° and then diluted the total quantity of gelatine goes into solution and hence practically the same gold number is obtained irrespective of the process of dilution.

The influence of the quality of gelatine on the peptising power of gelatine in cases of precipitates has been studied in the cases of silver and lead chromates. These substances were formed by mixing dilute solutions of the respective nitrates with the exact chemically equivalent amounts of potassium chromate. From preliminary experiments the quantity of gelatine was so adjusted that by using different volumes of the reacting substances, peptised solutions of different degrees of turbidities were obtained. To compare the turbidities of the different mixtures a simple arrangement was set up as shown in the diagram. The light is divided into two beams by means of the screen *S* containing two semi-circular apertures p_1 and p_2 . One beam of light passes through the liquid under examination contained in the cell *C*, whilst the other beam reaches the reflecting surface *R* after passing through a piece of milk glass *m*. Liquid is run into the cell *C* till the intensity of both the spots of

light on the screen *S*, which is protected from all extraneous light, is about the same. Two series of experiments were performed using fresh gelatine in one case, and the same amount of partially hydrolysed gelatine in the other case. 0.4 c.c. of a one per cent. gelatine solution were added to different volumes of the reacting substances, the total volume in each case being brought up to the same value. The results are given in the following table:—

	AgNO ₃ 3.502 per cent.	K ₂ CrO ₄ 2.0 per cent.	Turbidity readings.	
			Pure gelatine	Hydrolysed gelatine
1.	0.2 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	Completely precipitated.	Partially precipitated.
2.	0.3 c.c.	0.3 c.c.	Precipitated in 24 hours.	Stable sol.
3.	0.4 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	5.5 c.c.	11.3 c.c.
4.	0.5 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	6.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.
5.	1.0 c.c.	1.0 c.c.	4.5 c.c.	7.0 c.c.
6.	1.5 c.c.	1.5 c.c.	Precipitated on standing.	Partially precipitated.
7.	2.0 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	Immediately precipitated.	Immediately precipitated.

From the above it will be seen that partially hydrolysed gelatine is more efficient in peptising silver chromate than pure gelatine. Similar results were obtained with lead chromate.

It will be interesting to recall that Zunz (*Arch. Internat. Physiol.*, 1904, 1, 427) has obtained similar marked differences in the peptising properties of

albumoses, the decomposition products of egg albumin. The synalbumoses have no protective action on gold, whilst the proalbumoses have a fairly good peptising power (*cf.* Zsigmondy, *Chemistry of Colloids*, p. 108). It thus seems to be a general property shown by protein and similar bodies of being a better peptising substance when partially hydrolysed.

Summary.

1. Solutions of gelatine containing a certain amount of gelatose and other earlier hydrolysis products of gelatine have been found to be more efficient in peptising gold sols than solutions of purified gelatine.

2. Dilute gelatine solutions prepared from a one per cent. gelatine gel at 70° gave practically the same gold numbers and thus failed to show the effects observed by Elliott and Sheppard at 50°.

3. Partially hydrolysed gelatine is a better peptising agent for silver and lead chromates than pure gelatine.

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